

Use of diverse grazers

www.eurafagroforestry.eu/afinet/

In Finland, mainly sheep and cows are used in silvopastoral systems. However, there would be opportunities for using other grazers too, for example for enhancing biodiversity, offering opportunities for recreation and earning some additional farm income. For instance, free-range chicken exist in Finland but woodland chicken (free-range chicken with access to trees) are very rare. There would be an opportunity to increase woodland egg production. In the olden days, pigs were kept outside but nowadays almost all pig production has moved to indoor production. Here is an opportunity for sustainable meat production and improving animal well-being. Alpaca's can be used on rural tourism and well-being farms, and goats for producing goat cheese. Ostrich farms for meat production were popular in the end of the 1990's but nowadays this practice has almost disappeared. For more animals there would be opportunities to be used in agroforestry. The milk from water buffalo can be used for making special cheese; the most well-know is mozzarella cheese. Water buffalo's are very suitable as landscape grazers, also in more wet habitats such as shore meadows. Water buffalo's are not bothered by cold northern European conditions and they can stand temperatures as low as down to -30° C. Use of more diverse grazer communities can enhance landscape and farm diversity and make farms more resilient to climate change and market fluctuations. In addition, use of more diverse grazers may provide additional farm income.

Links:

Water buffalo's as landscape grazers:

https://www.maajakotitalousnaiset.fi/sites/default/files/attachment/esimerkkikortti14.pdf?fbclid=IwAR3gPbatxAs_MP2VJosXnlSOpqITfoOuv07X6qF9yRsg8wvNmcfFC67z6uY

Watch video: Finland's first waterbuffalo's getting used to the Finnish winter in Kangasniemi:

<https://www.maaseuduntulevaisuus.fi/maatalous/artikkeli-1.354415?fbclid=IwAR3WGdfUOCKY3pYeHR4kJIO9Vb3XdAObG5zcl57MV3jCNwNIP8mF8bl9E7s>

Photo by Michael den Herder

Michael den Herder

European Forest Institute